

Physicochemical Properties of Banana Fruit Starch and Starch Components

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Granular starches were extracted from banana fruits viz: Basrai, Harichal, Lalkel (variety of *Musa cavendishii*), Rajeli, Safed Velchi (variety of *Musa paradisiaca*) and studied for their intrinsic viscosity, alkali number, blue value, iodine binding capacity, and amylose contents. The starches were fractionated into their amylose (Fraction A) and amylopectin (Fraction B) components. Intrinsic viscosity, beta-amylolysis limit and unit chain length of amylose and amylopectin were studied. Beta-amylolysis of amylose varied from 76 to 98 percent.

THE bicomponent of starch granule was elegantly revealed by 'choch' who quantitatively separated amylose from complex formation with polar organic compounds particularly *n*-butanol. Bus. Muetgeert and Hiemstra^{2,3,4} carried out the fractional precipitation procedure for the separation of amylose and amylopectin. Tanret⁵ removed traces of amylose from amylopectin solution by adsorbing the amylose on cotton. Practically all the available information regarding starch structure has been derived from the work on cereal and tuber starches, chiefly corn and potato. It was therefore felt of interest to examine a fruit starch in order to ascertain whether or not its structure differed from that of cereal and tuber starches previously studied. The present investigation was therefore undertaken to study the physicochemical properties of the linear and branched components of the banana fruit starch.

Materials and Method:

Five varieties of banana fruits viz. Basrai, Harichal, Lalkel (variety of *Musa cavendishii*), Rajeli, Safed Velchi (variety of *Musa paradisiaca*) were selected for the present investigation. Basrai banana was obtained from Jalgaon district, while other varieties were obtained from Bassein road of Bombay. In order to get banana bunches of uniform maturity nearly 50 banana plants were

tagged at the time of inflorescence emergence in a nearby banana plantation, where uniform practices were maintained throughout the growing season. From the above lots two bunches, each of uniform development were harvested at 100 days of growth (full round shape) after inflorescence emergence. The bunches were brought to the laboratory immediately after harvesting and separated into hands.

Extraction of Starch:

Starch from the above varieties of banana fruits was extracted as the procedure outlined by Subrahmanyam⁶ *et al.* with some modifications.

1000 g banana fruits were peeled and cut into small pieces and then extracted with 2 litres of distilled water in a Waring blender in 100 g lots. Each lot was blended for about 2 mins. and slurry was filtered through 100 mesh sieve with gentle agitation. Filtrates were pooled together and treated with 1.0 g. of potassium metabisulfite ($K_2S_2O_5$) to inhibit browning. The liquid containing starch in suspension was strained through a set of sieve of decreasing mesh size to eliminate the fibre. Suspension liquid was decanted and sediment washed several times with distilled water. Starch was collected in ethanol and filtered on Buckner funnel with ethanol washing and dried at room temperature (26°-28°).

The starch was defatted, first by refluxing with petroleum ether followed by hot extraction with 85% methanol as described by Schoch¹.

Dispersion of Starch :

Defatted banana fruit starch (30.0 g.) was suspended in 500 ml. glass distilled water, purged with nitrogen, allowed to equilibrate at +4° for 16-18 hrs and sedimented starch granules were suspended in 100 ml. citrate buffer (pH 6.2, 1.0 M) under mild stirring. The slurry was added to 700 ml. of buffered urea solution (pH 6.2, 10 M) and urea for complete saturation of the solution. The mixture was purged with nitrogen and kept under mild stirring until complete dispersion of starch achieved, The dispersed starch solution was highly viscous and was precipitated with ethanol under brisk stirring for 2-3 hrs. The precipitate was collected by centrifugation and used for isolation of amylose and amylopectin by fractional precipitation.

Fractionation of starch :

20 g. of defatted dispersed banana fruit starch was suspended in 18 ml water and a boiling mixture of *n*-butanol : water (1 : 10) was slowly added with constant stirring. The paste was autoclaved for one hour at 18 lb. pressure. To the suspension a 1 : 1 mixture of butyl and amyl alcohol was added and suspension cooled slowly to 28°. The supernatant was added, siphoned off carefully and precipitated amylose was added and separated by centrifugation. Precipitate and supernatant were collected separately and precipitate containing amylose was recrystallised from boiling water in presence of *n*-butanol.

Amylopectin was precipitated from the supernatant by addition of an excess of methanol. 10 g of defatted cellulose powder treatment was given to remove traces of amylose by adsorption. Amylopectin was precipitated by the addition of excess of methanol followed by repeated treatment with cold fresh methanol and dried over P₂O₅ at room temperature.

Action of Taka-diastase on starch :

This was carried out according to the method used by Shantha and Siddappa⁷. The light transmission of the colour developed was measured on Beckman Model DU spectrophotometer at 650 nm.

Blue value of starch :

The method followed for the determination of

starch iodine blue value was essentially that of Kurasawa⁸.

Alkali number :

Alkali number of starch was determined by following the procedure as described by Kerr⁹.

Intrinsic viscosity :

This was determined by the method of Lansky¹⁰ et al as described by Kerr⁹. An Ostwald pipette No. 1 maintained at 35° ± 1° in a thermostat was employed for determining the specific viscosity. Intrinsic viscosity of banana fruit starch, amylose and amylopectin were determined.

Amylose content of starch :

Amylose content of isolated starches from bananas was determined by potentiometric titration according to Schoch¹¹. This involves the determination of iodine affinity for starch which corresponds to the linear content (or amylose content) of the given starch samples. Percentage of amylose was calculated from the relation

$$\% \text{ Amylose} = \frac{\text{mg bound iodine at zero intersect} \times 100 \times 100}{\text{sample weight in mg} \times 18.9}$$

Beta-amylolysis limit :

The β-amylolysis limit was measured using E. Merck analytical grade β-amylase (25 mgs), dissolved in acetate buffer (pH 4.7) at 30.0° ± 0.02°. After 48 hours of hydrolysis, reducing sugars were determined by alkaline ferricyanide method¹² using maltose hydrate as the standard. The β-amylolysis limit was calculated as the percentage of theoretical yield of maltose hydrate.

Determination of Number of Chains per molecule of amylose and amylopectin (Unit chain length) :

Starch fractions viz. amylose and amylopectin were oxidised with sodium metaperiodate using the procedure of Potter and Hassid¹³ as modified by Greenwood and Thomson¹⁴. The oxidation time used was 25-30 hrs. The average length of unit chain was expressed as anhydroglucose units. The outer chain length was calculated from

$$\text{Outer chain length} = \frac{\text{beta-amylolysis limit} \times \text{unit chain length}}{100} + 2.5^{15}$$

Results and Discussion

Enzymatic breakdown of starch by Taka-diastase is shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen from the

Fig. 1. Action of taka-diastase on banana fruit starch.

- Safed Velchi
- Basrai
- △ Lalkel
- Rajeli
- ⊙ Harichal

graph that hydrolysis of starch by Taka-diastase decreased rapidly at the beginning and then slowly after 15 minutes. Shantha and Siddappa⁷ have shown similar trend for tuber starches.

Table 1 represents the data regarding the physicochemical properties of isolated starch from different varieties of bananas. The microscopic examination of banana starch showed that they differed significantly in their sizes and varied from 30.3 μ to 59.5 μ . The intrinsic viscosities of banana starches were found in between 2.8–4.1. Shantha and Siddappa⁷ have reported the intrinsic viscosity of corn starch (1.5) and potato starch (2.0) but in the present investigation high values obtained

indicate that molecular weight of banana starch might be more than potato and corn starch. Alkali number ranged from 3.6–4.8. This number indicate the affinity of starch with alkali. Blue value for Safed Velchi banana starch was found to be low and also its amylose content. The apparently fine texture and superior quality of Lalkel variety might probably be due to its high amylose content. Iodine binding capacity ranged from 3.3–3.6. Basrai, Rajeli, Harichal banana starches were found to contain 20.80%, 20.24%, 20.0%, amylose respectively. Beta-amylolysis limit of banana fruit starch ranged from 58.8% to 67.5%. It was found that the conversion of starch to maltose in the hydrolysis was not 100 percent complete. The small difference in the values for whole starch may be due to the presence of low molecular weight amylose type molecule. Harichal, Rajeli and Basrai banana hydrolysed 61.8%, 60.3% and 64.4% respectively. The values above 70% for Beta-amylolysis limit are reported by Peit¹⁶ *et al.*

The characterisation data of amylose recrystallised from banana fruit starch are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF RECRYSTALLIZED BANANA FRUIT AMYLOSE

Variety	Iodine binding capacity %	Blue value as O.D. at 610 nm	Intrinsic viscosity in 1N KOH (η)	Beta-amylolysis limit %	Unit chain length
Basrai	18.9	0.9	4.2	82.3	257.1
Harichal	18.4	0.7	5.6	76.2	267.9
Rajeli	18.8	0.8	4.7	85.5	299.3
Lalkel	18.6	0.7	4.3	90.5	228.7
Safed Velchi	18.4	0.7	4.9	98.2	190.9

The recrystallised amyloses were readily soluble in water and had iodine binding capacities 18.4–18.9%. Their blue values were comparable except for low values obtained for amylose of safed velchi banana. The wave length range of maximum absorbance of iodine-amylose complexes was 650 nm reported by Otani and Takahashi¹⁷. The amyloses had

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF PURIFIED DEFATTED BANANA FRUIT STARCH

Variety	Average granular size in μ	Intrinsic viscosity in 1N KOH (η)	Alkali number	Blue value as O.D. at 610 nm	Iodine binding capacity %	Amylose contents %	Beta-amylolysis limit %
Basrai	30.3	3.2	3.6	0.5	3.6	20.8	64.4
Harichal	40.3	2.8	4.8	0.4	3.4	20.0	61.8
Rajeli	50.4	4.0	4.0	0.4	3.4	20.2	60.3
Lalkel	59.5	4.1	4.4	0.5	3.6	21.2	67.5
Safed Velchi	31.5	3.6	3.8	0.4	3.4	19.8	58.8

significantly different intrinsic viscosities and ranged from 4.2 to 5.6. Killion and Foster¹⁸ reported lower than the values $\eta = 4.28$ (0.5 M NaOH) for potato amylose. Beta-amylolysis limit of amyloses recrystallised from banana starches varied from 76.2% to 98.2% which were found to be higher than 68-78% range of corn, barley and wheat amyloses¹⁴. The unit chain length from periodate oxidation showed a range of 190.9-267.9 for amyloses. Harichal banana amylose showed as high as 267.9 units, per chain length whereas low value (190.9) was obtained for Safed Velchi banana amylose.

Table 3 throws light on the physicochemical

TABLE 3—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BANANA FRUIT AMYLOPECTIN.

Variety	Iodine binding capacity %	Intrinsic viscosity in 1N KOH (η)	Beta-amylolysis limit %	Unit chain length*	Outer chain length†
Basrai	0.5	1.2	62.2	13.7	11.0
Harichal	0.4	2.4	50.0	17.2	11.3
Rajeli	0.2	2.8	55.7	15.4	11.1
Lalkel	0.4	1.6	59.7	14.7	12.2
Safed Velchi	0.3	2.6	50.0	16.2	10.6

* From periodate oxidation data.

† Calculated from $\frac{\beta\text{-amylolysis limit} \times \text{Unit chain length}}{100} + 2.5$

properties of purified amylopectin from banana fruit starch. It can be seen from table 3 that purified amylopectins differed in their iodine binding capacity ranging from 0.2%-0.5%. The intrinsic viscosity (η) varied from 1.2 to 2.8. Basrai banana amylopectin had the lowest intrinsic viscosity (1.2) whereas Rajeli banana amylopectin had highest intrinsic viscosity (2.8). Beta-amylolysis limit of amylopectin differed remarkably and varied from 50% to 62.2%. Beta-amylolysis of amylopectin was found to be agreeable with the values reported by Manner¹⁹. Greenwood and Thomson¹⁴ reported the usual range of β -amylolysis limit of 56-58 percent for other cereal amylopectins. The unit chain length from periodate oxidation showed a range of 13.7-17.2 anhydroglucose units for amylopectins. The outer chain length calculated from β -amylolysis limit and

periodate oxidation were 10.6 to 12.2 anhydroglucose units. The average length of unit chain length for other cereal amylopectins¹⁴ ranged from 19-24.

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References

1. T. J. Schoch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2957.
2. W. C. Bus, J. Muetgeert and P. Hiemstra, *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 52, 13295, 13296, 14204, 17768,
3. J. Muetgeert, *Advance carbohydrate chemistry*, 1961, 16, 299.
4. R. L. Whistler and E. F. Paschall, *Starch Chemistry and Technology*, 1965, Vol. I, 331, 1967, Vol. II, 451.
5. C. Tanret, *Bull. Soc. Chem.*, 1915, 4, 17 and 83.
6. V. Subrahmanyam, G. Lal, D. S. Bhatia, N. L. Jain, G. S. Bains, K. V. Srinath, B. Anandswamy, B. H. Krishna and S. K. Lakshminarayan, *J. Sci. food agri.*, 1957, 8, 253.
7. H. S. Shantha and G. S. Siddappa., *J. food Sci.*, 1970, 35, 72.
8. H. Kurasawa, Y. Kanauti, I. Yamamoto, T. Hayakawa and I. Igaue, *Agri. Biol. Chem.*, 1969, 33, 793.
9. R. W. Kerr, "Chemistry and Industry of Starch", 2nd Ed. Academic Press N. Y., 1950, p. 675.
10. S. Lansky, M. Kooi and T. J. Schoch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 4066.
11. T. J. Schoch, *Methods in Carbohydrate Chemistry*, 1964, 4, 157.
12. American Association of Cereal Chemists. St. Paul Minn "Cereal laboratory methods", 7th Ed. 1962.
13. A. L. Potter and W. Z. Hassid, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3488.
14. C. T. Greenwood and J. Thomson. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962 222.
15. S. Peat, W. J. Whelan and G. J. Thomson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4546.
16. S. Peat, W. J. Pirt and W. J. Whelan, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1952, 705 and 714.
17. Y. Otani and S. Takahashi, *Hakko Kogaku Zasshi*, 1958, 36, 448; *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 17415.
18. P. J. Killion and J. F. Foster, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1960, 46, 65.
19. D. J. Manner and A. Wright, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1597.